

Open Science & Impact Festival 2025

Programme

8.30 Registration and morning coffee

9.30 Opening words

- Piia Seppänen, Vice-rector for research, University of Turku
- Sami Niinimäki, Counsellor of Education, Ministry of Education and Culture

10.00 Key note: *Transition to Open Science – Why and How*

- Frank Miedema, Emeritus professor, Utrecht University
- Commentary:
 - Juuso Repo, Senior Researcher, INVEST Research Flagship Centre
 - Anne Marjamäki, Head of Business Development, member of the InFLAMES executive team, University of Turku

11.00 Key note: *Open Science as a transformation of the research system*

- Ismael Rafols Garcia, Senior Researcher, University of Leiden
- Commentary:
 - Jari Lavonen, Professor, University of Helsinki

12.00 Lunch

13.15 Workshops

14.15 Panel discussion: *The importance, challenges and support structures of open science and research impact*

Moderator: Ilari Sääksjärvi, Professor of Biodiversity research, Director of the Biodiversity Unit, University of Turku

Panelists:

- Nora Fagerholm, Associate Professor in Human-Nature Interactions and Sustainability, DIWA Flagship, University of Turku
- Taina Saarinen, Research professor, Director of Finnish Institute for Educational Research, EDUCA Flagship, University of Jyväskylä
- Juhani Knuuti, Professor of Cardiovascular imaging, Administrative Director of InFLAMES Research Flagship, University of Turku
- Jani Erola, Professor of Sociology, Director of INVEST Research Flagship Center, University of Turku

15.15 Closing words: *The Beauty of Science Communication*

Reetta Kettunen, Secretary General, Committee for Public Information

Networking over cocktails

Event ends by 17.00

Opening words

Piia Seppänen,

Vice-rector for research, University of Turku

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Opening words

Sami Niinimäki, Counsellor of Education,
Ministry of Education and Culture

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MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND CULTURE
FINLAND

Open Science & Impact Festival

Sami Niinimäki
Turku 14.5.2025

Current affairs in higher education and science policy

Aims of Finnish Higher Education and Science Policies towards 2030

50 %

50 % of young adults will hold a higher education degree.

4 %

The level of RDI investments is 4 % of GDP. 1/3 of the investments will be public and 2/3 private.

LUMI

The European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU)

LUMI is located in Kajaani, Finland

1 SYSTEM
380 Petaflop/s
PEAK PERFORMANCE

COMPUTING POWER EQUALS
1.5 MILLION
MODERN LAPTOP'S
CAPACITY

100%
HYDROELECTRIC
ENERGY

Future vision for higher education and research

- Updating and renewing the previous vision was launched November 2024
- Outlining long-term development needs and outlooks towards 2040
- Supporting quality, internationality and diversity
- Exploring different alternatives and models for improving the Finnish higher education and research system on the bases of the changes in national and international operating environment

About open science and impact

A national research information system

Share of publications by open access type

Note. The same publication can be both self-archived and published in an Open Access channel or a hybrid journal. Therefore, the sum of the publication counts for different open access types differs from the total number of open access publications.

Share of open publications by publication forum level (2024)

Share of open publications by sector (2024)

Share of open publications by discipline (2024)

Share of open publications by main publication category (2024)

Open access publishing in Finland

Share of open access publications by main discipline

Scientific impact of open and non-open access publications

- The figure includes all categories of open access by Web of Science: <https://webofscience.help.clarivate.com/en-us/Content/open-access.html>
- Publications with no information on open access or discipline have not been included.
- The index describes the proportion of the most cited publications; the global average in each discipline is 1.0. If the index is above 1, the publication is cited more than the global average.

Number of publications by main discipline 2018–2021

Natural sciences	10,123
Bio and environmental sciences	5,104
Engineering and technology	8,447
Medical and health sciences	11,117
Agricultural and forest sciences	1,415
Social sciences	8,688
Humanities	2,334
General scientific journals	1,378
TOTAL	48,606

Source: Web of Science based data from Clarivate Analytics, bibliometric calculations CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd, 2024.

Scientific impact of publications in European countries

Top 10 index in 2018–2021

The index describes the proportion of the most cited publications; the global average in each discipline is 1.0. If the index is above 1, the publication is cited more than the global average.

Development of scientific impact of publications in Finland and reference countries

The index describes the proportion of the most cited publications; the global average in each discipline is 1.0. If the index is above 1, the publication is cited more than the global average.

Development of scientific impact of Finnish publications

- The top 10 index describes the proportion of the most cited publications; the global average is 1.0. If the index is above 1, the publication is cited more than the global average.
- At least one of the authors of an international co-publication is from outside Finland. The authors of a national co-publication are from at least two different Finnish organisations. All authors of one organisation's publication work in the same Finnish organisation.
- The label numbers are the number of publications in Finland during the four-year period 2018–2021.

■ International co-publication (19,350)
■ All Finnish publications (48,606)
■ Single-organisation publication (16,421)
■ National co-publication (12,835)

Source: Web of Science based data from Clarivate Analytics, bibliometric calculations CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd, 2024.

Researcher's Profile Tool, from indicators to narrative

The screenshot shows the 'Researcher's Profile Tool' interface. At the top, the URL 'research.fi/en/mydata' is visible. The page title is 'Researcher's Profile Tool' with a logo on the left and 'Log in' and 'In English' on the right. The main heading is 'Compile a public profile of your data in the Research.fi service'. Below this, a paragraph explains that users can compile a public profile from their ORCID and home organisation information. There are three main sections: 'New user? Start here:' with a 'Create Profile' button; 'Additional information:' with a 'Quickstart guide' button; and 'Already have a profile?' with a 'Log in' button. On the right side, a diagram illustrates the data flow: 'ORCID' and 'RESEARCH.FI' (with a user icon) feed into a 'Profile' box, which then feeds into a 'Publications' box. Both 'Profile' and 'Publications' boxes feed into two 'ORGANISATION' boxes, each with a university icon.

Challenges still remain

Rising costs of publishing

Retrieved from Research.fi 13.5.2025. Source: Survey data collected by The Coordination of Open Science and Research, FinELib, and the Open APC initiative.

Research suffers from geopolitical challenges: case atmospheric observations

- Russian Arctic is a key component in climate change
- Cooperative plans for large scale atmospheric observations in 2021–2022, cancelled in February 2022.
- All data flows stopped from on-going measurements

The Global Atmospheric Watch (GAW) Network

▲ GAW Global Station ● GAW Regional Station ■ Contributing Station
Open symbols denote closed or inactive stations.

Slide by professor Tuukka Petäjä, University of Helsinki

Concluding remarks

Ways to advance open science and impact

- FAIR Principles
- Data skills and lifelong learning
- Reform of research assessment
- Clear legislation to support digital research
- Monitoring of outputs and costs
- Responsible international cooperation

Many thanks!

Key note: *Transition to Open Science –
Why and How*

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Transition to Open Science: From Open Access to Reform of Recognition and Rewards

Frank Miedema

Utrecht University, UMC Utrecht

'Open Science : The Very Idea'; Springer 2022. Open Access.

'The University in Transition', Kummeling et al, 2024

Universiteit Utrecht

Transition to Open Science: why?

**Just some of
the problems of
the science
system**

- Competitive and non-cooperative practices
- Quality and Replication crisis
- Expensive commercial publication markets
- Privatization and problems of knowledge ownership / knowledge access
- **Relationship with society**

Open Science: the promise (1)

The overall aim of Open Science is to increase the quality, progress and scientific & societal impact of research and scholarship.

To achieve these goals in the practice of Open Science

Engage -when appropriate- with relevant and representative stakeholders from society to:

- Define problems to be investigated; discuss ongoing research
- Actively promote that the results of any kind provide guidance for implementation and action(s) in the specific contexts in the real world.

Open Science: the promise (2)

To achieve these goals in the practice of Open Science

- Share research results, if possible, in several stages of the work and publishing these results and papers
Open Access
- Adhere to Open Data and Code (Software)

To facilitate this:

- **Change Incentive and Rewards accordingly**

Metrics shape Science

- ***Novelty and quantity*** are dominant over quality, replication, relevance and impact
- **Short-termism and risk aversion** because of 4-year funding cycles
- **Fields with high societal impact, but low impact in the metrics system suffer** (applied vs basic; SSH vs STEM)
- **The national and institutional research agenda is thus not properly reflecting societal (clinical) needs and disease burden**

F. Miedema, Open Science : The Very Idea'; Springer 2022. Open Access

The classical image of science distorts academia through flawed academic hierarchies

1. Natural and biomedical science >> Social science >> humanities ('**physics envy**')
2. Theoretical & pure science >> applied science and technology
3. Curiosity-driven research is the best for solving societal problems (the linear model)
4. Science should be autonomous, not interfered by external publics or politics and their problems
5. Scientific knowledge is neutral; scientists are not responsible for the knowledge they (don't) produce

The Scientific Field: Professional Interests, Elites, Stratification, Power Struggle, and Economics

Figure 3. The credibility cycle, adapted from Latour and Woolgar (1986). Points at which organizational devices connect to the cycle are shown

Problems of the Current Reward System in Science

Society is largely absent from the *credibility cycle*

Quality in Quantitative terms:
- number of articles, journal impact factor, citations, H-index
- amount of funding obtained

Hypercompetition for limited funds

Too little room for Team-Science, Multidisciplinarity & Diversity

Money

- **Most papers still behind paywalls**
- **Data not shared**

The classical image of science distorts academia through flawed academic hierarchies

‘We are witnessing a key moment in modern science, as universities and funding agencies are stepping up their role to deliver societal impact and drive social and economic change. A key part of this transition is better and more responsible rewards and recognition in research. Now, more than ever, European and global leaders need to come together to discuss the fundamental values underpinning research assessment. If we are successful, we will deliver a platform for the Presidency to truly strengthen the collaborative excellence and impact of research and researchers. ‘

David Budtz Pedersen, Aalborg University, May 2025 LinkedIn.

EU Open Science Agenda since 2016

• Citizen Science/Public Engagement/IMPACT

- Open Access
- FAIR Data
- European Open Science Cloud

- Research Integrity
- Skills and Education

- Rewards and Incentives
- Research Indicators/ Meaningful Metrics

<https://www.openscience.eu/open-science-policy-platform-final-report/>

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/statistics/policy-support-facility/mle-open-science-altmetrics-and-rewards>

TOWARDS OPEN SCIENCE

@UMCUTRECHT: Inclusive set of generic indicators for research quality and impact (in use since 2016)

Structure	Leadership & culture
	Collaborations with stakeholders
	Continuity and infrastructure
Process	Setting research priorities
	Posing the right questions
	Incorporation of next steps
	Design, conduct, analysis
	Regulation and management (OA, FAIR data sharing)
Outcomes	Research products for peers
	Research products for societal groups
	Use of research products by peers
	Use of research products by societal groups
	Marks of recognition from peers
	Marks of recognition from societal groups

Utrecht University - TRIPLE model

TRIPLE: Team Spirit as the default approach to working in academia

- TEAM
- RESEARCH
- IMPACT
- PROFESSIONAL PERFORMANCE
- LEADERSHIP
- EDUCATION

TRIPLE MODEL

OPEN SCIENCE RECOGNITION AND REWARDS

Systemic Interventions to improve quality, impact and integrity at all levels

Engagement of societal stakeholders in problem choice research and evaluation

Inclusive indicators

Quality
Societal Impact
Use in and outside academia
Process Indicators

OPEN PEER REVIEW
POST PUB PEER REVIEW

OA publishing
FAIR Data and Code sharing

The Promise of Open Science

Open Science will:

At the organizational level improve academic culture and the daily practice of research

Foster responsible research conduct and research integrity at several levels

Will improve the interaction with society and increase the impact of science

Room for everyone's talent

towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics

> Diversifying and vitalising career paths

We enable more diversity in career paths and profiles for academics.

> Achieving balance between individuals and the collective

We assess academics based on both their individual and their team performance.

> Focusing on quality

In our assessments of academic performance, we increasingly focus on quality, content and creativity.

> Stimulating open science

We encourage academics to share their research outcomes with society.

> Stimulating academic leadership

We stimulate good academic leadership at all levels.

National Strategic Evaluation Protocol The Netherlands 2021-2027

Evaluation is in relation to the unit's strategy

Three criteria:

Research Quality, Societal Impact and Viability

Four Aspects:

- **Open Science practices and efforts**
- **PhD policy and Training**
- **Academic Culture (Openness, Safety, Inclusiveness, Research Integrity)**
- **Human Resources Policy (Diversity, Talent Management)**

The many ongoing Initiatives and Actions

- <https://sfdora.org> **The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment**
- **2016 EU adopts Open Science as the standard for Horizon Europe 2021**
- <http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-policy-platform> Including Open Science Career Advancement Matrix
- **Coalition S and Plan S**
- **UNESCO** <https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science>
- <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org>
- <http://responsiblemetrics.org>
- VSNU, NWO, NFU: www.vsnu.nl/Room for Everyone's Talent;
- https://www.vsnu.nl/files/documenten/Domeinen/Onderzoek/SEP_2021-2027.pdf

Coalition of the Willing to Reform Research Assessment: CoARA

Is about *implementation* of improved evaluation.
Lead by EUA, EU DG R&I and Science Europe.
400+ organisations from 40+ countries since
2022

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/reforming-research-assessment-agreement-now-final-2022-07-20_en

<https://coara.eu/>

**Commentary: Juuso Repo,
Senior Researcher, INVEST Research
Flagship Centre**

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Commentary: Anne Marjamäki,
Head of Business Development,
member of the InFLAMES executive
team, University of Turku

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Commentary talk

DEBATE IN ACADEMIC DISCUSSION

Protection of Research results vs Open Science

The word **patent** originates from the Latin **patere**, which means "to lay open" (i.e., to make available for public inspection)

Patents are negative rights, not positive privileges

A patent provides its owner with the right to prevent commercial utilization of invention (manufacture, sale, marketing) in a specific region/country for restricted period of time

Scientific articles are published behind paywalls

one of the main goals of Open Science is to share the results, increase publishing in Open Access and increase the quality of research

Patent publications are open to everyone via patent databases

patent needs to give detailed description of solution, must be repeatable (quality) and can be invalidated

Espacenet = a global free-of-charge and easy to use patent database managed by the WIPO (<https://worldwide.espacenet.com/>); **PATENTSCOPE** = a global free-of-charge and easy to use patent database managed by the WIPO (<https://worldwide.espacenet.com/>)

Why should I care ?

- 70-90 % of information in patent publications cannot be found anywhere else
- No point in exploring already known topic/solved question – State-of-the –art analysis prior research plan
- By exploring patent landscape you can identify possible partners for your research project
- Most funding agencies appreciate utilization plan with a possibility for IPR generation
- Patenting does not prevent publishing; just file the patent application first

Research vs Development in Pharmaceutical industry

Mean cost of developing a **new drug** was \$172.7 million but increased to **\$515.8 million** when cost of failures was included
JAMA Netw Open. 2024;7(6):e2415445.

- The process from discovery to market takes ~ **10 to 15 years**.
- Currently, only 5/5000 compounds advance to clinical trials from preclinical phase
- About 90% of drugs that enter clinical trials fail

Academia and start up community is a source of new drug targets and lead molecules for Pharma industry (Research and Discovery). Development work, including regulatory aspects, productization and marketing is done by Pharma industry

Every successful drug holds the potential to save or enhance countless lives.

THANK YOU !

Keynote: *Open Science as a
transformation of the research system*

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Open Science and Impact Festival,
University of Turku, 14th May 2025

¿(How) Can Open Science Transform Research Systems towards more impact?

Ismael Ràfols

INGENIO (CSIC-UPV), Universitat Politècnica de València, València

UNESCO Chair on Diversity and Inclusion in Global Science

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University, Leiden

The argument

- **Is science fulfilling its social and policy expectations?**
 - yes, major contributions: health, nutrition, AIs - but with dark side: obesity, aging, AI for whom?
 - is science really addressing major societal challenges? is it improving life of the poor populations?
 - in some instances, research has created major problems: climate change and environmental destruction, financial innovation...
- **Will “open science” improve the values of science and the societal contribution?**
 - What types of Open Science are being implemented?
 - Do they address the issues raised?
- **From access to outputs → to judicious connections or productive interactions.**
 - Simple putting data in open access will not suffice
 - What REALLY matters are the interactions and the outcomes of research
 - Shifting research assessment towards contextual evaluation

**How does research
contribute to society?**

Three frames of innovation policy (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018)

1. Linear model (postwar until 1980s)

- Science → Technology → Innovation → Well-being

Innovation

Transformative Innovation
Policies Consortium
<https://www.tipconsortium.net>

Three frames of innovation policy (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018)

1. Linear model (postwar until 1980s)
 - Science → Technology → Innovation → Well-being
2. Innovation Systems (early 1990s until late 2000s)
 - Chain-linked model and interactions between stakeholders are key for innovation.
 - STI interactions → Innovation → Economic Growth → Wellbeing

Transformative Innovation
Policies Consortium
<https://www.tipconsortium.net>

Wrong priorities: Misalignment btw research efforts and societal (health) needs

% disease burden in DALYs (blue) vs. % publications (red)

Kumar et al. (2023)

Questionable social relevance: Research on Podoconiosis: ¿genetics, soils or shoes?

Podoconiosis is a neglected tropical disease and recognised by the **swelling it generates to the feet.**

The disease is due to people **walking barefoot on irritant minerals** that can be found in clay soil in Cameroon and Ethiopia.

A research project may involve:

- Soil analysis
- Geo-statistical mapping of the areas most affected
- Genetic predisposition analysis

→ **However: access to shoes would largely solve the problem**

Coburn, Chataway and Ohid (2022)

Negative effects

Climate change

Urban development

Cultural and ethnic suppression

Asbestos

Instabilities in financial innovation

Three frames of innovation policy (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018)

1. Linear model (postwar until 1980s)
 - Science → Technology → Innovation → Well-being
2. Innovation Systems (early 1990s until late 2000s)
 - Interactions between stakeholders are key to produce innovation.
 - STI interactions → Innovation → Economic Growth → Wellbeing
3. **Inclusive or transformative innovation (2010s...)**
 - **Innovation NOT necessarily positive – climate change, pollution.**
 - **Situated and contextual: what? where? who? for whom?**
 - **Attention to diverse types of knowledge -- given uncertainty**
 - **Plural views on directions/goals of research and innovation**
 - **Mission-orientation, grand challenges, SDGs...**
 - **Environmental, social issues, etc.**

Innovation

Transformative Innovation
Policies Consortium
<https://www.tipconsortium.net>

The right to science as a human right

Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948)

Article 2

Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, **without distinction of any kind**, such as race, colour, sex, **language**, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. (...)

Article 27a

Everyone has **the right to freely to participate** in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to **share in scientific advancement and its benefits**.

- The right to participate in science
- The rights to benefit from scientific advancement
- ...**without distinction of any kind**

10th December 2023

Is Open Science the
response?

Umbrella term... multiple concepts ...and many umbrellas

Perspectives on OS: One Term, Five (+) Schools of Thought

From a literature review:

‘...openness could refer to pretty much anything: The process of knowledge creation, its result, the researching individual him- or herself, or the relationship between research and the rest of society.’

Fecher & Friesike (2013)

Perspectives on Open Science: Euro. Comm.

- European Com. (2016) *Open Innovation, Open Science Open to the World.*

‘Open Science represents a new approach to the scientific process based on **cooperative work and new ways of diffusing knowledge** by using **digital technologies** and new **collaborative tools.**’

- EC Open Science Webpage (2023)

Open science is a policy priority for the European Commission and the standard method of working under its research and innovation funding programmes **as it improves the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research.**

When researchers **share knowledge and data** as early as possible in the research process with all relevant actors it helps diffuse the latest knowledge.

And when partners from across **academia, industry, public authorities and citizen groups are invited to participate** in the research and innovation process, creativity and trust in science increases.

Perspectives on Open Science: UNESCO

UNESCO Recommendation 2021:

‘...open science is defined as an **inclusive construct** that combines various movements and practices aiming to make **multilingual** scientific knowledge openly available, **accessible and reusable for everyone**, to increase scientific **collaborations and sharing of information** for the **benefits of science and society**, and to **open the processes** of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication **to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.**’

What is Open Science?

According to 2021 UNESCO Recommendation

1. Open Scientific Knowledge

- OA Publications
- Op Research Data
- Op Educational Resources
- Op Source Software
- Open Hardware

2. Open Science Infrastructure

- Physical
- Virtual

**Outputs
-object oriented**

What is Open Science?

According to 2021 UNESCO Recommendation

Dialogue with other knowledge systems

- Local communities
- Indigenous peoples
- Marginalised scholars

Processes,
subject-oriented

Engagement of Societal Actors

- Citizen and Participatory Science
- Scientific Volunteering
- Crowdsourcing
- Crowdfunding

OS @UNESCO: Core Values and Guiding Principles

Growing pains with Open Science

The problems with focussing only on access to research outputs

Open Access is progressing - but inequity may be increasing

... but they have different implications...
for example in terms of equity and diversity.

Trends in OA appear to be positive

Plural dimensions
Trends in OA by type

Effects or Outcomes:
OA pubs by demography

When more OS does not lead to better OS... ...more OA has gone against OS values

Open Access publications in Gold Open Access may increase number of publicly accessible pubs...

BUT some forms of OA:

- barriers to equity and fairness in publishing (e.g. in North/South and male/female OA)
- problems of quality and integrity (lack of rigorous reviewing: MDPI & Frontiers)
- challenge to collective benefit (more visibility to topics of the rich countries – which pay APCs?)

Do Open Outputs lead to the desired Outcomes?

The focus should be on outputs (paper, open data sets, software pieces)... ? or one the uses and demands? Assumptions driving OS policies might be wrong.

- Is Open Access leading to broader readership outside of academia? **Not large, but not negligible**
- What is the evidence of re-use of OD sets by other researchers? **Unclear. Under which conditions there is re-use?**
- Evidence of re-use of open software? **Yes. perceived as very high and impactful.**

Re-using Open Data. EC report (2020)

Problems with some implementations of Open Science

Sabina Leonelli (2023):

“...the interpretation of openness as the sharing of resources, so often encountered in OS initiatives and policies, may have the unwanted effect of **constraining epistemic diversity and worsening epistemic injustice**, resulting in **unreliable and unethical scientific knowledge**. “

“...some OS policies – despite their good intentions and progressive slant – [are] acting as a **reactionary force which reinforces conservatism, discrimination, commodification and inequality in research**, thus ultimately closing down opportunities for inquiry in a disastrous reversal of what they set out to achieve.”

Contextualised Openness

From access to outputs → to meaningful connections

- *Ross-Hellauer has stressed that enabling access is not enough to foster equity in science in the face of huge disparities in resources (Ross-Hellauer et al., 2022).*
- *Chan proposes that ‘the ability to **participate, to connect, and to co-produce knowledge** with others who share common concerns is **far more important than simply access** to content or resources’ (Chan et al., 2020, p. 2).*
- *Leonelli argues that ‘... from being solely a question of sharing resources, openness is thereby conceptualized as **the opportunity to make and maintain connections among relevant stakeholders** (...) in ways that help to develop ever more relevant forms of interaction with the world’ (Leonelli, 2023, p. 66).*

Contextualised Openness

“...there is no single or universal concept of OS that is sufficient to encompass the diversity of knowledge traditions and practices from around the world. Hence the term OS and the notion of “openness” is highly situated (...).

Our collective observations therefore challenge the tendency to define Open Science as a set of technical infrastructure, workflow, protocols, and licensing conditions that can be universally applied regardless of context, history, and human agency.”

Leslie Chan (2020)

Shift in focus from outputs / objects to processes / interactions

QUALITIES of the outputs matter for values

Open Research Datasets: FAIR:
Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable?

CARE: Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics

Educational Resources:
how appropriate for specific audience? which language, which gender, etc.?

1. Open Scientific Knowledge

- OA Publications
- Op Research Data
- Op Educational Resources
- Op Source Software
- Open Hardware

2. Open Science Infrastructure

- Physical
- Virtual

**Outputs
-object oriented**

Shift in focus from outputs / objects to processes / interactions

Dialogue with other knowledge systems

- Local communities
- Indigenous peoples
- Marginalised scholars

Processes, subject-oriented

Engagement of Societal Actors

- Citizen and Participatory Science
- Scientific Volunteering
- Crowdsourcing
- Crowdfunding

PROCESSES
(over time):

CommunicationS and interactionS

between
researchers, with
stakeholders are
often iterative.

Diverse contexts of use

Very different
missions and unequal
access to resources

Strategies in participatory and transdisciplinary research

- Build on established strategies of participation and transdisciplinarity
- Potential combination with new digital media, e.g. in citizen science.

Communicating scientific knowledge for beneficiaries

- **Using the local language and formats adapted to users / beneficiaries**
 - To reach out relevant knowledge to practitioners (e.g. in medicine)
 - Briefs for policy makers
 - History and social science books to reach out to citizens
 - Educational resources for High School in local language
 - Documents for agricultural extension
 - Scientific literacy against ‘fake news’ (trust in science)

Helsinki Initiative on
multilingualism led
by Federation of Finnish
Learned Societies
(Janne Pölönen)

The local space as a space for public engagement and citizen science

¿**Qué pasa Riachuelo?** (What's happening in Riachualo?)

A platform for engaging local citizens in the cleaning up of a river in the periphery of Buenos Aires, Argentina)

The groups affected by the pollution of the river participate with local knowledge, shaping the agenda, bringing research data and interpreting findings for change.

Valeria Arza (Univ. San Martín)

Conclusions

OS strategies (interactions) need to be fit for a purpose and a context

1. One of the goals of Open Science is to improve the societal contributions of research (**which can be problematic!**)
2. Goal - not only to have social impact, but to have impact **to fulfil societal needs and demands.**
3. Current implementations of OS based on **making outputs openly accessible have not been shown to have major effects on societal impact** - and may lead to inequality within science.
4. Shift from OS as access to products to **meaningful connections or of interaction processes** between stakeholders.
5. **Contextualising openness is crucial** so that OS has the desired effects, including in research assessment.

Back up slides

INGENIO (Polytech València) and CWTS (Leiden Univ.)

- Centres on “Research on Research” and how science contributes to innovation and social change
- Focus on evaluation of research and its impact
- Evaluation perceived as a major barrier against OS
- My involvement with OS:
 - EC Expert Group on Indicators for Researchers' Engagement with Open Science (2017-19)
 - UNESCO working group on Monitoring OS (2022- present) part of UNESCO Chair

*Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics
Nature (2015)*

UNESCO Chair on Diversity and Inclusion in Global Science

With Rodrigo Costa, Louise Bezuidenhout and André Brasil

(CWTS, Leiden)

Three main lines (with a focus on research evaluation):

- Investigate epistemic/topic diversity: e.g. health priorities
- Studies on (in)visibility of scientific research from Global South
- Supporting developing OS monitoring in the context of UNESCO

The right of science

Is the right of science recognised?

Is the right of science upheld, actively protected by laws?

Is the right of science somehow enforced, implemented?

Perspectives: Manifesto of OCSDNet

(Open and Collaborative Science in Development Network)

For all the claimed benefits of OS...

- ... current model is NOT making science a more inclusive practice.
- ... many scientists continue to be underrepresented and excluded
- ... new technologies exclude those with limited digital rights .
- ... citizens rarely get to shape the research agenda.

Principles

- knowledge commons
- cognitive justice
- situated openness
- right to research
- equitable collaboration
- inclusive infrastructures
- use knowledge as a pathway
to sustainable development

The vision of the evaluation of reforms: Contextualisation. Pre-eminence of the qualitative and responsible use of indicators

Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

Lat Am

Highlighting:

- recognition of various contributions
- contextualization
- support for open science

- integrity
- stakeholder participation
- invest. collab. and transdisciplinary

Nature Editorial, 13 Jan. 2022
**Research evaluation
needs to change
with the times**

The focus on a narrow set of metrics leads to a lack of diversity in the types of leader and institution that win funding.

EDITORIAL | 27 July 2022

**Support Europe's bold vision
for responsible research
assessment**

There have been many initiatives to combat the distorting effect of research assessment exercises. The latest looks like it might work

**UNESCO Recommendation
on Open Science**

Nov. 2021

RESEARCH CULTURE
Empowering researchers with
a thriving research system
integrated in society

Commentary: Jari Lavonen,
Professor, EDUCA Flagship, University of
Helsinki

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Comment to plenary: Open Science as a transformation of the research system

Open Science & Impact Festival 2025

Turku 14.5.2025

Open science as a movement ...

... aims at making scientific research, data, and dissemination accessible to all levels of society to increase transparency, reproducibility, collaboration in research, and accelerate scientific discovery and innovations.

Open science encompasses practices such as:

- **Open Access:** Making research papers freely available online.
- **Open Data:** Sharing research data so others can use and analyse it.
- **Open Source:** Providing access to the software and tools used in research.
- **Open Peer Review:** Making the peer review process transparent and accessible.
- **Citizen Science:** Involving the public in scientific research.

Open Science Annual Review in 2024

(<https://blogs.helsinki.fi/thinkopen/open-science-review-2024/#avott>)

- An update of the Declaration for Open Science and Research
- Long-term accessibility is still a challenge in the commitments to openness.
- The policy for edited books and monographs was prepared in 2024 and will be published in 2025.
- The roadmap for funding open science was prepared in 2024, will continue during 2025.
- Almost two-thirds of universities in Finland, including the University of Helsinki, have achieved the highest level of open science and research.
- The guide, [How to Become a Citizen Scientist: A Beginner's Guide](#) was published in August 2024
- [The guide for describing research data](#) has been published to describe the data and the main metadata elements for all disciplines.
- The University of Helsinki was ranked 24th (89,7 % were open access pub.), and the University of Jyväskylä 31st in terms of the share of open-access publications ([CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition 2024](#))
- Jouko Rikkinen, who started the Pinkka learning environment, was receiving the University of Helsinki Open Science Award in 2024

- The greatest potential for improvements in open science is open education and open educational resources.
- Open science is not recognised in merit systems

General principles in open publishing at the University of Helsinki, 29.1.2025

- Academic publications and theses produced at the University of Helsinki are openly available by default.
- The University promotes publishing openly in high-quality academic publication channels, regardless of the research field.
- The University aims to promote the immediate open access of new publications.
- The University has an overall picture of the costs of open access publishing and aims to ensure that they remain reasonable.
- The University develops its own assessment practices in such a way that activities to promote open access to research publications and, more generally, open publication culture, are considered when evaluating researchers and research.
- The University guarantees the long-term availability of research publications produced within its scope.

Panel discussion: *The importance, challenges and support structures of open science and research impact*

Moderator: Ilari Säaksjärvi, Professor, Director of the Biodiversity Unit, University of Turku

Nora Fagerholm, Associate Professor, DIWA Flagship, University of Turku

Taina Saarinen, Research professor, Director of Finnish Institute for Educational Research, EDUCA Flagship, University of Jyväskylä

Juhani Knuuti, Professor, Administrative Director of InFLAMES Research Flagship, University of Turku

Jani Erola, Professor, Director of INVEST Research Flagship Center, University of Turku

Closing words: The Beauty of Science Communication

Reetta Kettunen, Secretary General, Committee for
Public Information

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Get inspired.

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Workshops

- Track 1: *"Only open science makes an impact"* – *Ways to share your research for impact* → Manu 1-4, BioCity
- Track 2: *Impact Café – Strategies to Amplify the Impact of Your Research* → Showroom, Joki, 1st floor
- Track 3: *Research collaboration for impact – How to engage with businesses successfully?* → Workshop, Joki, 3rd floor

Avoine tiede

Track 1: Only open science makes an impact” – Ways to share your research for impact

Henriikka Mustajoki & Aleksi Husso

<https://avointiede.fi/en>

Please find a seat with max. 5 other participants!

Goals of the workshop

- Understand the role of open science for making an impact in society
- Learn strategies for making your research outputs more accessible and impactful
- Develop skills to design your research to be as open as possible and as closed as necessary
- Create a first draft for opening your own research outputs

Avoim tiede

Intro

Why open science?

- More exposure for your hard work
- Taxpayers get value for their money
- Compliant with grant rules
- Public can access the findings
- Research can influence policywork

Societal impact = change in the world

- Changes in our society are made by people
 - If you want to make a difference, you need to change how people think
- Decision makers, politicians, officials the public and future adults
- Researched knowledge is often a key to new ways of thinking

How open science leads to impact

- Knowledge becomes:
 - more accessible,
 - transparent,
 - and usable beyond academia
- Increasing resilience in times of crises

Avoine tiede

Activity 1

10 min group work

Activity 1

What kind of research outputs could you and/or your research group produce?

Who would be interested in your research and the results?

Avoim tiede

Activity 1 debrief:

Share one idea from each group

Avoim tiede

Activity 2

10 min group work

Activity 2

Choose one of the research outputs discussed previously:

What are you trying to achieve?

Who are you trying to influence?

How would you make your research as open and accessible as possible with the previous points in mind?

Avojn tiede

Activity 2 debrief

Each group shares at least one example on how they would open their research and how that would lead to impact

Avojn tiede

Wrap up and take home messages

Avoim tiede

Thank you for joining and sharing!

<https://avointiede.fi/en>

SUOMALAINEN TIEDEAKATEMIA
FINNISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCE AND LETTERS
ACADEMIA SCIENTIARUM FENNICA

Enhancing Research Impact Through Knowledge Brokering

*Iiris Koivulehto & Laura Väliniemi,
Finnish Academy of Science and Letters*

How do you feel about making an impact?

First things on your mind?
Hard, easy, hopeless, inspiring, bullshit?

**Science
Communication
and Advice**

**Knowledge
Brokering**

What?

Understanding

Tools

Reflections

Why?

Information overload

Decision-makers (in politics or private sector) work in a fast-paced environment surrounded with endless amounts of information.

The conditions for the experts to follow scientific research and most updated results has become unrealistic.

💡 Plan your effort!

Start here!

Core Principles

#1 Interacting with the stakeholders from the start of the research project.

#2 Work in collectives and communicate big.

#3 Divide the work based on everyone's interests and strenghts.

1. Channels for Research Impact

QUESTIONS

What have you done before? How it went?

What was the impact?

What new you could try? Why?

Dialogue
practices

Written practices

Media based
practices

Others

Group Work

2. Opportunities for Impact

QUESTIONS

What have you done before? How it went?
What was the impact?
What new you could try? Why?

Group Work

3. Researcher's role

SYNTHESISER

Research reviews

→ When existing results meet the need.

COMMENTATOR

Recommendations, statements, policy briefs

→ Needs cannot be directly met with the existing research.

ADVOCATE

Public statements

→ Researcher has recognised an important objective or policy measures that are supported by research.

QUESTIONS

What have you done before? How it went?
What was the impact?
What new you could try? Why?

Group Work

MY SOCIETAL INTERACTION PLAN

(name here:)

1. MY RESEARCH

Which societal themes are relevant for my research and expertise? Which societal stakeholders are relevant for my research? And to which policy-making levels (ministry, municipality etc.) are they connected?

2. MY GOALS

I aim to contribute to the following things:

... and have the following impacts on them:

3. MY NETWORK

I'm part of the following networks and communities (for instance research groups, scientific societies)?

Are there other networks or communities, which I should join?

4. TO ACHIEVE MY GOALS...

... with whom could I cooperate with (e.g. close colleagues, scientific societies, cross-sectoral consortia)?

... to whom should I try to have an impact on

... which of the following interaction practices are important for achieving my goals?

5. MEANS OF INTERACTION

Which means of societal interaction have I already used?

Dialogue practices	Written or media based practices
seminar or panel with policymakers <input type="checkbox"/>	policy recommendations <input type="checkbox"/>
workshop or round table with policymakers <input type="checkbox"/>	popular book <input type="checkbox"/>
training professionals and teaching students <input type="checkbox"/>	opinion piece for news media <input type="checkbox"/>
expert hearing <input type="checkbox"/>	social media content and blog post <input type="checkbox"/>
direct contact with policymakers <input type="checkbox"/>	exhibition, show or concert <input type="checkbox"/>
communicating with stakeholders outside of policymaking <input type="checkbox"/>	guideline to support professionals <input type="checkbox"/>
	IT product <input type="checkbox"/>
	(code, algorithm, program, device)
	appearance in radio or tv show <input type="checkbox"/>

(Mark the practices you've already taken part in. If a practice is not listed here, add it to the empty slots.)

It would be especially interesting to develop my skills related to the following interaction practices:

6. MY ROLE(S) AS A RESEARCHER

Which researcher role (synthesiser, commentator, advocate) do I find the most suitable or comfortable, and why?

Which role feels most uncomfortable, and why?

7. MY NEXT STEPS

During the next months I will (e.g. find out about on-going policy-making, join a network connected to my research topic, locate new key stakeholders, organise a workshop).

In the more distant future, I would like to try out.

Part 1. Introduction to interaction between research and policy

Course material

From science to decision-making

– how to enhance the impact of research

Thank you!

Iiris Koivulehto & Laura Väliniemi

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Iiris

Laura

Research collaboration for impact – How to engage with businesses successfully?

Open Science & Impact Festival 2025

14.5.2025

Outi Vanharanta & Petro Poutanen

VAIKUTTAVUUS
SÄÄTIÖ

Download the report:

www.vaikuttavuussaatio.fi/en/publications/

The Finnish Research Impact Foundation (FRIF)

VAIKUTTAVUUSSÄÄTIÖ
The Finnish Research Impact Foundation

- **Annually, an average of 84 applications**
- **A total of €11.7 million in funding granted to 60 projects since 2020**
- **47 post-doctoral researchers and 13 professors have worked in close collaboration with companies with the support of the funding**
- **The market value of the foundation's capital is about €77 million**
- **Established in 2019**

Funding opportunities

TIA Postdoc

Funding for a post-doctoral researcher for 2 years, with 50% of the project at the partner company. Supervised by an academic PI and an Industrial Supervisor.

TIA Professor

Funding for a professor-level researcher for 12 months within a 3-year project. Enabling research in an industrial context.

TIA Seed

Seed funding for a top researcher new to Finland to initiate industry collaboration with multiple companies.

Guide for academics to ensure successful industry academia collaboration projects

VAIKUTTAVUUSSÄÄTIÖ
The Finnish Research Impact Foundation

Guidebook's content

- 1. Finding a partner company**
- 2. Ensuring smooth and impactful collaboration**
- 3. Maximizing the benefits of the company period in Tandem Industry Academia Projects**

When looking for a potential partner company

Reaching out to potential partners

Aligning expectations

Establish clear objectives at the beginning of the project and confirm that both parties have a shared understanding of them.

Ensure ongoing communication throughout the project.

Define publication rights and data sharing early.

Tips for TIA researchers: How researchers can get the most out of their time at the company?

Engage actively

Participate in team activities and embrace opportunities to contribute beyond your immediate project.

Adapt to new ways of working

Learn the preferred communication channels and etiquette in the company and stay open to the company's organizational culture.

Be proactive

Actively seek networking opportunities and take initiative to connect with colleagues.

Communicate effectively

Share updates on your progress regularly and inform colleagues about your schedule and availability.

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